

Determinants of Length of Stay of Snakebite Victims in a Hospital. Statistical Modeling Approach

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Abstract:

In snakebite envenoming research, occurrences of snakebite are predominantly in the poor, rural communities within the tropical and subtropical countries throughout the world. The most affected in health are the people who engage in agricultural or pastoral activities living in those areas. In recent times, there are increasing in cost and the burden of snakebite envenoming in health facilities. In this paper, we investigate factors that are associated with length of stay of hospitalized snakebite victims using a proportional odds model with maximum likelihood estimation. A secondary data is obtained from the Ghana Health Service particularly in the Upper West region of

Ghana, and a purposive sampling adopted to obtain other information through administering questionnaire. Findings show that, gender, age, dependence status, marital status, body part of bite, first aid and treatment are significant determinants of length of stay. Furthermore, the study revealed that victims who were given first aid as a primary care stayed longer in the health facility compared to those not given first aid. This result is unexpected since first aid is generally administered purposely to reduce the complication as a result of the snakebite and hospital cost. In this study, the dominant first aid is the traditional medicine approach. Hence, further studies regarding how the people in those rural areas administer traditional medicines as first aid after snakebite envenoming is recommended.

Keywords: Snakebite envenoming, First aid, Proportional odds model, Length of stay.

Introduction

There are over three thousand seven hundred and eighty (3,780) species of snakes existing globally and a fact that approximately five (5) million people are victims of snakebite annually with about 81,000-138,000 people dying of snakebite each year (Ramdhani et al., 2020).

Snakebite envenoming is a major cause of death especially in the tropical and rural communities where majority of the people are poor and cannot afford proper medical care with limited health facilities. The incidence of snake envenomation is relatively higher in the Latin America, South and South-eastern Asia and Sub-

Sahara Africa (Mana et al., 2019). In these tropical and rural communities, farming, hunting, animals rearing, and fishing are common economic activities and people who engage in these activities come into direct contact with many snakes of different species making them susceptible to snake envenomation (Mensah et al., 2016; Ochola et al., 2018; Yakubu et al., 2019).

The commonest snakebite in Africa is in the Savannah region of West African, where the *carpet* or *saw-scaled viper*, *E. ocellatus*, is responsible for the majority of morbidity and fatality (Yakubu et al., 2019). In the Northern regions of Ghana, recent studies revealed an incidence of 86 per 100,000 population (Yakubu et al., 2019) and a case fatality rate of 3% (Musah et al., 2019). Most of these snakebite victims in the Northern regions of Ghana are rural farmers who are financially less endowed and are unable to afford proper medical care. A study conducted by (Okumu et al., 2019) revealed that, increasing length of stay (LOS) of hospitalized snakebite victims increases the cost incurred. The high cost of treatment magnifies the economic and health burden on these victims. In places where the incidence of snakebite is high, there is a tremendous impact and pressure on health-care facilities, health-care workers and hence worsening the medical cost of victims.

Some of the recent studies have intensified the call to minimize the incidence and the deadly effects of snakebite in rural areas with many focusing on reporting the incidence (prevalence), the epidemiology, treatment, and risk factors of snakebite mortality (Chaudhari et al., 2014; Mensah et al., 2016; Ruha et al., 2017; Ochola et al., 2018; Bhaumik, et al., 2020; Bowden et al., 2022). Other studies have shown that snakebite cases go unreported and others resort to traditional means of treating the envenomation (Sapkota et al., 2020; Steinhorst et al., 2021). A recent study by (Özbulat et al., 2021) show factors influencing the LOS of snakebite victims in Turkey. In their research they focused more on clinical factors and relied solely on univariate analysis and proportions as measures of associations. Ignoring the natural ordering of LOS have effect on model stability.

In this study, we investigate the factors that are associated with LOS by using the ordinal multinomial logistic regression. Some of the factors considered are exposures to treatment, clinical factors, circumstances surrounding the bite, and the victim's pre-hospital care. It is worth noting that, the complexity of a snakebite venom and the management of the outcome of bite is evidenced in the outcome of treatment and the length of hospitalization. Furthermore, longer length of hospitalization increases the chances of reinfections in the hospitals, which becomes additional burden and cost to treatments. Therefore, LOS is a crucial measure of the outcome of snake envenomation which can help hospital management mitigate the efficiency and sufficiency of health-care facilities as well as the overall burden of snakebite on the people of the Upper West Region where the risk of snakebite is very high.

Materials and Methods

Data Collection

This study was carried out in the Upper West Region of Ghana. The region forms part of the six regions that make up the Northern Belt. Multiple data sources were used to collect the data for analysis. A secondary data on the clinical presentation and treatment outcomes during hospital admissions were obtained from the Ghana Health Service (GHS) particularly in the Upper West region of Ghana. A purposive sampling scheme was adopted to gather thorough data on 250 victims' sociodemographic backgrounds, the exposure and circumstances surrounding the bite, the victim's pre-hospital care. After a patient's initial presentation to the hospital, a questionnaire was designed for the victims or close relatives and victim's information and other relevant features were recorded in 2021.

Statistical Model

The main outcome variable of the study is length of stay of hospitalized snakebite victims (LOS) measured on an ordinal scale with four (4) levels. Generally, the formulations of the multinomial

models are shown below. We define the LOS with it four levels as follows:

$$LOS = \begin{cases} 1 & < \text{one day} \\ 2 & 1 \text{ to } 3 \text{ days} \\ 3 & 4 \text{ to } 6 \text{ days} \\ 4 & \geq 1 \text{ week} \end{cases}$$

Proportional Odds Model

The proportional odds model compares the probability of an equal or smaller outcome $LOS \leq j$ to the probability of a larger outcome, $LOS > j$. It is given by (1).

$$\text{Log} \left[\frac{P(LOS \leq j | \mathbf{X})}{P(LOS > j | \mathbf{X})} \right] = \alpha_j + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_i x_i$$

$$j = 1, 2, 3 \quad (1)$$

To find the specific probabilities for each category in (1), where Y is LOS , we note that,

$$P(Y = j) = P(Y \leq j) - P(Y \leq j - 1)$$

$$j = 1, 2, 3, 4 \quad (2)$$

where $P(Y \leq 0) = 0$ and $P(Y \leq 4) = 1$

here,

$$P(Y = j) = \frac{\exp(\alpha_j + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_p x_p)}{1 + \exp(\alpha_j + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_p x_p)} \quad (3)$$

where x_1, x_2, \dots, x_p are set of independent variables with associated set of coefficients. The

$$L(\boldsymbol{\beta}) = \prod_{i=1}^n \left[\prod_{j=1}^J \pi_j(x_i)^{y_{ij}} \right] = \prod_{i=1}^n \left[\prod_{j=1}^J (P(LOS \leq j | x_i) - P(LOS \leq j - 1 | x_i))^{y_{ij}} \right] =$$

$$\prod_{i=1}^n \left[\prod_{j=1}^J \left(\frac{\exp(\alpha_j + \boldsymbol{\beta}' x_i)}{1 + \exp(\alpha_j + \boldsymbol{\beta}' x_i)} - \frac{\exp(\alpha_{j-1} + \boldsymbol{\beta}' x_i)}{1 + \exp(\alpha_{j-1} + \boldsymbol{\beta}' x_i)} \right)^{y_{ij}} \right] \quad (6)$$

The Fisher's scoring algorithm was used to obtain the maximum likelihood estimators, after maximizing $L(\boldsymbol{\beta})$, (Agresti, 2003).

proportional odds model is more parsimonious than the multinomial logit model because it uses fewer parameters to explain the effect of the independent variables on the log odds of being in category j or below.

The odds ratio (OR) for the i^{th} independent variable is given by

$$OR = e^{\beta_i} \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) is interpreted as, the odds of being in category j or below is e^{β_i} times the odds of being in a higher category for each unit change in the i^{th} variable when other predictors are held constant, for a i^{th} continuous independent variable. The applicability of model (1) however depends on the assumption of proportional odds which purports that, the effect of independent variables is constant over each level of the LOS outcome variable.

Model Estimation

To estimate the parameters in (1), the logits of cumulative probabilities are one technique to employ category ordering,

$$P(Y_i \leq j | \mathbf{x}) = \pi_1(\mathbf{x}) + \dots + \pi_j(\mathbf{x}), \quad j = 1, \dots, 4 \quad (5)$$

We let (y_{i1}, \dots, y_{ij}) be the binary indicators of the outcome for subject i . The likelihood function of the model is given by

Assessing the Goodness of fit of the Model

This study intends to use the likelihood ratio test to assess the goodness of fit for model (1). The

test nests a reduced model within full model and compares the deviances of these two competing models (Ameade, Bonney, & Boateng, 2021) . The likelihood ratio test has an approximately chi-square with degree of freedom, $p(k-2)$. Where p is the number of independent variables and k is the number of levels of the outcome variable. The formulated hypotheses are as follow: H_0 : There is no significant difference in the performance of the two models. H_1 : There is significant difference in the performance of the two models

The test statistic is given as;

$$G^2 = -2LL_0 - (-2LL_1) \quad (7)$$

Where, L_0 is the deviance of the reduced model and L_1 is the deviance of the full model.

When the null hypothesis is not rejected, the reduced and more parsimonious model is adopted for inference.

Results

In building the model, we considered twelve (12) independent variables after a preliminary analysis from a total of twenty-five (25) variables. Some missing observations were recorded and that reduced the initial sampled data from 250 to 230. To visualize the most frequently reported reactions exhibited by victims due to the envenomation, we employ a word cloud shown in Figure 1.

From figure 1, the commonest reactions showed after the envenomation were bleeding, swelling, pain and headaches. Other reactions were dizziness, coagulopathy and vomiting.

Figure 1. Word Cloud of Reactions of Victims after Envenomation

Table 1 shows that majority of the snakebite victims are males (70.9%) and less than a third were females (29.1%). Most of these victims (57.8%) were within the age group 15-25 years and about 6% were above age 50 years. About 65% of the victims were bitten while in the farm whereas 35% were hunting, fishing, carrying firewood, walking or in the house with majority of the bites (80%) spotted at the lower limbs. Also, about 66% of victims received various first

aid and 34 % did not receive any first aid of any form. Majority of the cases were rushed to the hospital within one day after envenomation whilst 3% of the cases took more than a day to report to the health facility. About 64 % of the patients spent between 1 to 3 days in hospital admissions while 6% spent less than a day in the hospital. From this results, there is evidence of LOS in the hospital.

Table 1. Frequency Distribution of Relevant Variables

Variable	n(%)	Variable	n(%)
Gender		First Aid	
Male	163(70.9)	Yes	152(66.1)
Female	67(29.1)	No	78(33.9)
Age		Given treatment	
15-25	133(57.8)	Yes	211(91.7)
26-40	63(27.4)	No	19(8.3)
41-50	20(8.7)		
≥ 50	14(6.1)		
Dependence		Treatment type	
Yes	109(47.4)	ASV	50(27.7)
No	121(52.6)	Polyvalent	180(72.3)
Marital Status		ATS	
Married	107(46.5)	Yes	149(64.8)
Divorce	18(7.8)	No	81(35.2)
Separated	13(5.7)		
Not married	83(36.1)		
Widow/widower	9(3.9)		
Education		LOS	
No Education	66(28.7)	< 1 day	16(7.0)
Basic level	103(44.8)	1 - 3 days	147(63.9)
Secondary level	29(12.6)	4 - 6 days	53(23.0)
Tertiary	32(13.9)	>7 days	14(6.1)
Activity		Part of Bite	
Farming	150(65.2)	Hand	46(20.0)
Others	80(34.8)	Leg	184(80.0)

Source: The Author’s computation, 2023

From Table 2, means to hospital, treatment type, ATS, and Time lapsed were not significant predictors of LOS on snakebite victims after hospitalization ($p > 0.05$). These insignificant predictors were subsequently dropped from the model and a reduced model was obtained with eight (8) predictors. An ANOVA test was conducted to ascertain the appropriateness of using the reduced model instead of the full model. The test shows that the reduced model was significant ($p=0.559$). Hence, we adopted the reduced and more parsimonious model with only eight (8) predictors.

Table 3 shows the results of the likelihood ratio test for the significance of the eight (8) predictors in the reduced model.

Table 2. Likelihood ratio test of the Full model

Variable	LR Chisq	p-value
Gender	6.56	0.010
Age	16.51	0.002
Dependence	32.06	<0.001
Marital Status	68.53	<0.001
Education	25.35	<0.001
Part of bite	7.17	0.007
First aid	4.33	0.037
Means to hospital	0.00	0.948
Treatment	16.22	<0.001
Treatment Type	1.58	0.209
ATS	1.54	0.215
Time lapse	0.68	0.411

Source: The Author’s computation, 2023

Table 3. Likelihood Ratio Test for the Reduced Model

Variable	LR Chisq	p-value
Gender	6.14	0.013
Age	16.23	0.003
Dependence	31.09	<0.001
Marital Status	79.57	<0.001
Education	26.56	<0.001
Part of bite	11.84	0.001
First aid	3.78	0.049
Treatment	14.91	<0.001

Source: The Author's computation, 2023

The residual deviance statistics was used for the overall test of significance of the model. A reported residual deviance statistic of 315.58 divided by the number of predictors (8) to obtain 39.45 has an approximately chi square with 1 degree of freedom ($p < 0.001$). This shows that at least one of Gender, Dependence, Age, Education, Marital status, body part of bite and First aid are associated with LOS. In Table 4, the reduced proportional odds model, gender, dependence, age, education, marital status and part of bite were significant predictors of LOS. The results of the ML estimates are shown in Table 4, for the significant effect of gender, dependence, first aid, part of bite, and education on LOS.

Table 4. Fitted Model using Maximum Likelihood

Variable	Coefficient (β)	t	OR = $e^{-\beta}$
Gender (Male) Female	1.052*	-2.416	2.863
Age (16-25) 26-40 41-50 ≥ 50	-2.381* -1.932 0.138	-2.187 -1.913 0.163	10.82 6.90 0.871
Dependence (Yes) No	-3.056*	-5.013	21.24
Marital Status(Single) Divorce	-1.141 2.422*	-1.588 3.299	3.131 0.089

Separated Not married Widow/widower	0.962 -7.622*	1.741 -5.555	0.382 2042.02
Education (None) Basic level Secondary Tertiary	-1.328* -3.274* -2.650*	-2.413 -4.252 -3.529	3.774 26.409 14.148
Part of bite (Hand) Leg	-1.248*	-3.385	4.171
First aid (Yes) No	0.784*	1.934	0.457
Treatment (Yes) No	-2.858	-3.644	17.423
Constants 1 2 2 3 3 4	-9.909 -3.778 -1.432	-6.735 -3.268 -1.239	- - -

Note: * 5% level of significance

Discussion

The prevalence of Snakebite envenomation have been studied in the Upper West region of Ghana. Our results have shown that the most common reaction after envenomation are bleeding, swollenness in the body area of bite and pain. Snakebites are common in males because household heads are mostly farmers. Majority of the bites are in the legs of victims an indication of expose to risk of bite without any boot for protection. The result of the parsimonious model in Table 4 shows that the effect of gender; the log odds of a longer duration of stay in the hospital is 1.052 higher for females than males when all other predictors are constant. The corresponding odds ratio, 2.86 means the odds of a longer duration of stay in the hospital significantly increases by 186% ($p < 0.05$) if the snakebite victim is a female. For dependence, the log odds of a longer duration of stay in the hospital is 3.056 times higher for snakebite victims who are dependents than those that do not depend all else equal. The corresponding odds is 21.24 which means, the odds of a longer duration of stay in the hospital is 21.24 times significantly higher if the snakebite victim is not dependent as compare to those that depend on others. This phenomenon may be due to the influence of cultural practices where dependent victims are given enough care and emotional support hence improving the healing

process and shortening their length of stay in the hospital. For snakebite victims within age 16 to 25, the odds of a longer duration of stay in the hospital is significantly 10.82 times ($p < 0.05$). For victims who are separated, the odds of a longer duration of stay in the hospital is highly significantly 91.1% ($p < 0.05$) less than the odds of the victims who are married all else equal. For a victim who is a widower/widow, the odds of a longer duration of stay in the hospital is 2.042 times the odds of a married victim all else equals. For education, the odds ratio of 3.774 means the odds of a longer duration of stay in the hospital significantly increases by 277% ($p < 0.05$) if the snakebite victim has no education than if he/she has a basic education. Also, for victims who have secondary education, the odds of a longer duration of stay in the hospital is highly significantly 26.41 times ($p < 0.05$) the odds of those who do not have any education, all other equal. For those who have tertiary education, the odds of a longer duration of stay in the hospital is 14.15 times the odds of victims who do not have any form of education. For part of bite, the coefficient tells us that, the log odds of a longer duration of stay in the hospital is 1.248 higher for a bite at the leg than the hand when all other predictors are constant. The corresponding odds ratio, 4.18 means the odds of a longer duration of stay in the hospital significantly increases by 318% ($p < 0.05$) if the envenomation is at the leg than the hand. For those who did not receive treatment, the odds of a longer duration of stay in the hospital is significantly 17.42 times ($p < 0.05$) the odds of those who received treatment all others equal.

First aid was significant in the full model in Table 3 but marginally significant in the reduced model. This could be due to the presence of other collinear variables that confounded the true relationship between first aid and LOS. Snakebite victims who were given first aid stayed longer in the hospital which maybe that the type of first aid can be interrogated. This could be as a result of inappropriate use of first aid since wrong administration of first aid could worsen the condition of victims which translates to longer duration of stay in the hospital (Özbulut et al., 2021). Moreover, it was also established

that even most health experts overestimate their knowledge in snakebite management (Ameade, Bonney, & Boateng, 2021).

Conclusion

As discussed above, findings showed that, gender, age, dependence, marital status, part of bite, first aid and education were significantly associated with LOS. Other variables such as means to the hospital, treatment type, time lapsed before victim was taking to the hospital, Tetanus Antitoxin (ATS) were not significantly associated with LOS. We found that, victims who were given first aid rather stayed longer in the health centers which was unexpected since first aid is generally administered purposely to reduce the complication of the bite. Hence, we recommend that, further studies be conducted to ascertain the appropriateness of the use of first aid among the people of the Upper West Region of Ghana whenever there is a case of snakebite

Author Contribution

N.K. Frempong conceptualize the idea, supervised the data analysis and wrote the manuscript. R.K. Avuglah wrote the main manuscript text. J. A. Anane, obtained the data and wrote the main manuscript. J. A. Atambire proof read the manuscript and prepared the manuscript for submission. All authors reviewed the manuscript

Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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